

INTER-CHARACTER CONFLICT AND SOCIAL CONFLICT

Hamidova M.O.

Candidate of philological sciences, professor, Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13891124>

Abstract. *Each era has its own problem, concept, poetry and image. This situation affects not only the person, but also the activity of the society and determines its direction. This article discusses the novel "Olaboji" by Shukur Kholmirzayev.*

Keywords: *thematic framework, image system, ideological direction, artistic analysis, character, anthropocentric, conflict between characters, social conflict, skill in prose, individual style, inner life of characters, mental experiences, intelligence, meaning spiritual world, writer's fantasy.*

Shukur Kholmirzayev is one of our leading writers who gained attention with his individual style, expression methods, tone of image, and rhythm in the complex and difficult genres of our literary prose, such as narrative (novella), story, short story, novel. His heroes are the owners of progressive ideas who analyze their "I" deeply, have a sharp observation, are bright in terms of their national nature, have a rich spiritual world, and look at our values with a new look. The confusion of times can be observed in the images created by the writer, who understood the hero's axis by connecting it with his intelligence.

In other words, the inner world of the hero acquires a relatively corrupt and unstable state under external influence. Through mental suffering, they try to understand themselves and come to a state of balance. The increasing attention to the depiction of conflicts in human nature and the expression of tension in his psyche naturally requires deepening of the lyrical tone in literary works, reflection of the spirit of time and place, and active use of dialogue and monologue forms. It seems that the heroes created by Sh. Kholmirzayev are simple, somewhat stubborn, and have a clear spirit, who act according to their heart's desire.

Each writer has his own way of seeing, perceiving, understanding and explaining the world, the experience of emotions gained in the process of creative mastering of the world. When thinking about the writer's skill, style and visual art, there is a need to act based on these elements [1, 16].

"The artistic plots formed on the basis of works of art show the scenes of life in constant motion. A writer should understand that he should not only draw a landscape with a pen, but also with the medium of words, and when drawing, he should not depict people motionless like an artist, but should show them in independent movement with words, in the struggle of groups or individuals", says M. Gorky [2, 144].

So, the plot of a work of art cannot live without conflict. Conflict (Latin *cyflictus*-disagreement, approach) is a face-to-face struggle between persons participating in a work of art, or a mental conflict between a hero and his surroundings, and himself. Conflict is the main force that drives the plot. As conflicts in life are colorful, so conflicts are manifested in works of art in different ways and forms. There are three types of conflict: the conflict and struggle of the heroes of the work; conditions, collision with the environment; internal struggle with oneself.

Shukur Kholmirzayev effectively used all three types of conflict in his novel "Olaboji". For example, the conflicts between the main character of the novel, Ulton, and the general secretary of the district, Toqliboy Kochkharov, can be an example of the conflict between the heroes of the

work. Ulton Sultanov's struggle against the injustices occurring in the workplace and around him is an example of the second type of conflict.

The conflict is manifested in the worldview of the writer, how he perceives and understands reality, life, the world and man. In the internal conflict, it is seen as a conflict between the hero's feeling of his duty and his weak mental side, his emotional suffering, and his condition. As an example of this, we can cite Ulton Sultanov's conflicts in his inner world, for example, conflicting thoughts about his relationship with Bahar, conflicting thoughts and experiences related to his path.

There are domestic, moral, social, political, philosophical and other types of conflict in terms of the direction of the topic. In the course of events, social conflict can turn into a philosophy of political conflict. Its essence is closely related to time and space. There will be such a conflict that they will disappear over time. For example, the works created in the ancient world are based on the conflict of fate and divine power in the works of the Middle Ages. In the era of romanticism, the conflict between reality, environment, conditions and the ideal, between good and evil, spiritual freedom and life concerns prevailed, and in the era when realism was celebrated, the essence of man, his desire, and his potential are on the ground of socio-historical conditions. There are such eternal themes in which the conflict is interpreted based on the spiritual requirements and needs of each era. In the Soviet era, when socialist realism prevailed, social-class antagonism was placed on the ground of conflict, and it was demanded to solve this conflict in a revolutionary way, between individual morality and collective consciousness, between the spirit of private property and the public, people's interest. Criticism of soviet system was forbidden, and because of this, the "theory" of non-conflict arose in the literature. Avoiding sharp conflicts in life, portraying reality, life, showing a person as a puppet, a robot was the main sign of the literature of that period.

Due to the national independence, the creative method of Uzbek literature has become a realistic method, it has become a criterion for truthfully depicting life and man, deeply revealing the scope and nature of conflicts in reality, and rationally describing the difficulties and complex processes in the development of a person and society. But the writer does not copy the conflicts in reality as they are into a work of fiction. On the contrary, he selects them, summarizes them, and makes them even sharper. It reveals and explains its essence. Shukur Kholmirezayev's novel "Olaboji" is also written in this style, and conflict plays a big role in revealing the psyche of the characters.

That is why they act according to their spiritual world and skills in concrete life situations. They are looking for themselves. In this process, the thoughts of the writer about the person and his experiences and destiny are also materialized. This situation requires the reader to bring the world of his imagination closer to the essence of literary characters. Without it, it is impossible to develop the nature of the characters and the influence of the social conditions of a certain period on the individual's psyche. It is understood that the comprehensiveness characteristic of Sh. Kholmirezayev's style is also expressed in the attitude of the heroes of certain novels to the life events, the coverage of the intellectual and emotional world.

In the process of artistic expression, the comparison of the admiration felt by the beauty and love of mother nature with the roughness of the heart is important in understanding the creative credo of the writer. Because Sh. Kholmirezayev considers a person to be a part of existence. The desire to harmonize these two separate worlds ultimately comes from the desire to raise the tenderness of feelings, the feeling of harmony, and the sincerity of expression in the human child.

It is possible to observe such qualities as the height, majesty, nature, tolerance, tenderness of the mountains in most of the characters created by the writer. Undoubtedly, this situation is a product of the writer's views on the twin nature of man and nature.

The impartiality of Sh. Kholmirezayev's attitude to the characters indicates the reader's confidence in the power of observation. After all, the dreams, worries, and thoughts of the characters are related to the virtues and defects of human spirituality, social and household problems. That is why he analyzes readers and tries to draw his own conclusions. The writer observes the principles of contemporary social justice through the prism of conscience and faith of an individual.

It describes his spiritual development in connection with national and universal values. In the nature of his characters, there are sometimes cases like drinking and smoking, and the writer aims to show the reasons that gave rise to this behavior, rather than condemning such vices. As a result, it becomes possible to reveal different levels of suffering and experiences related to belonging to the nation, at the same time feeling of helplessness, and artistic embodiment of the impact of social changes on the human soul.

Usually, in the nature of rural people, dependence on age-old traditions and traditions is somewhat stable. But the huge changes in social life, the economic difficulties of the 80s and 90s brought out mental conditions that were not visible in the nature of the nation at the previous stages of development. Being surrounded by family and livelihood worries and not being able to find ways out of the real situation has also led to the rupture of some human relationships. But he could not extinguish the human kindness in nation's treasury. In the analysis of these processes, the writer follows the path of analyzing images based on the requirements of honesty, conscience, and faith. He is able to instill in his works the confidence and hope that the presence of kindness, dignity, patience, human sympathy, unconditional generosity, and sincerity will guarantee the survival of the nation from changes.

In the novel "Olaboji" (1992), the author writes about the complicated and difficult life and fate of the leading character Ulton. As a man of conscience and faith, Ulton, a whole man, is deceived at every turn. He is cruelly deceived not only by strangers, but also by his teacher, relatives, and wife. The writer explores the hero as a highly spiritual person who has advanced not only from those around him in terms of his views, behavior and aspirations, but also from society as a whole. He is forced to move in the same orbit with people who are against the dimensions in which he lives. That is why it is so difficult. Because it is impossible to measure Ulton's spirituality and spiritual world with everyday worries and household measures. The inability of the individual and the society to merge with each other leads to the evaluation of the world outside the main character as "Olaboji" (a monstrous creature) in the eyes of the reader who evaluates Ulton's world and artistic reality.

So, in the novel, the problem of the individual and the society is presented in an extremely sharp way and is solved in an unexpected way. The critical spirit that appeared in the writer's "Last Stop" in the 70s of the last century, in the novel "Olabo'ji" sometimes appeared on the top of the orphaned mountain, roaring and muttering. Therefore, the author gave a symbolic meaning to the name of the novel.

In order to prove the change in the nature of some characters, if they describe it by reflecting their relationship to the events that are inextricably linked with them among the extraordinary acute events taking place in society, some writers manage to change the character of

the heroes and characters through a single detail [12, 24]. In fact, in the work of every creator, it serves to open the author's idea, connecting all the events. "An interesting detail, a beautiful fragment increases the value of the work, if it serves the realization of the idea with this interest and beauty" [10, 123], says the writer Abdulla Qahhor. The writer used the detail of the bear to reveal the spirit of Ulton, the main idea of the work.

It seems that when the writer is just an executor of the social order, not when he appears as an intellectual fulfilling his civic duty, but when he appears as a writer expressing his feelings based on the deep beliefs of our ancestors, reality and can approach human relations in a new way. In a word, he is one of the writers who strives to connect his artistic research with the methods of expression of world literature, to reflect the human personality from different angles, to illuminate the spiritual basis of his thoughts and actions.

In general, this novel invites the reader to think about human fate. Ulton's innocent love is trampled and his life is derailed. Every reader who has read the novel will not be indifferent to the fate of the characters.

REFERENCES

1. Boltaboyev H. Prose and style. - T., 1992. - 30p.
2. Boboyev T. Basics of Literary Studies.-Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2002.-B.144.
3. Hamidova M. O/ Shukur Kholmirzaev- a creative exposes person and society's illnesses // International Scientific Journal science and innovation, Series C, Volume 3, Issue 1, January 2024.- P.109 - 113.
4. Hamidova M.O.Writing skills and artistic tools. "Science and innovation" International scientific journal. Volume 2. Issue 4 April. 2023. Pages 125-127.
5. Hamidova M.O. Shukur Kholmirzayev's ability to create the character of a national hero // Berlin SCIENCE, RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT# 25.- 30.01.2020-31.01.2020.- B.209-214.
6. Hamidova M. The artistic and stylistic uniqueness of Shukur Kholmirzayev's stories // Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2021.- No. 4.- B.331.
7. Hamidova M.O.Shukur Kholmirzaev's skills of national character creation // Science and innovation international scientific journal. Volume 2, Issue 12, December 2023.- P.104-110.